

COMMUNICATIVE STRATEGIES AND VOCABULARY EXPANSION WHEN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECONDARY LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article deals with the problem area of intensive teaching of English as a secondary language. Conceptual ideas on the formation of communicative competence are realized on the basis of expanding the vocabulary of the English language in order to verify the developed methodology. The following article describes the methodical and pedagogical techniques of working with ESL vocabulary and identify the mechanisms that contribute to the psychological conditions of active vocabulary acquisition.

Key words: communicative strategies, vocabulary, lexical units, lexical skills, communicative competence, speech exercises.

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The distribution of knowledge is carried out according to the principle of social fields, not only in the scientific, but also in the ordinary sense. Any person who is engaged in in-depth study of foreign language, thinks about how to increase the vocabulary of that language. This aspect is paramount to success. Students must have a high level of motivation to learn lexical units. The level of motivation development depends, first of all, on the teacher's experience and the relevance of the material being studied. In everyday situations, language learners are often confronted with unfamiliar words and phrases that hinder their understanding of the language. In addition, learners have difficulty in situations where language barriers prevent them from expressing themselves effectively. Electronic dictionaries have become an easy way to overcome this problem. However, do students really improve their communicative competence by depending on electronic dictionaries? How can they teach them to rely less on dictionaries and more on their own language abilities? The fact that the dictionary of the language contains about 300 thousand words is only of theoretical interest for beginner to learn this language. Almost the main principle for the reasonable organization of their studies, especially at the initial stage, is the economy of words. One needs to learn to memorize fewer words, but do it as best one can. This approach is directly opposite to the leading principle of "suggestopedia" with its emphasis on the abundance of words presented to the student. In suggestopedia it is known that a beginner should be literally "showered with words" and offered to memorize 200 new words every day. Anyone will have difficulty remembering a large number of words with which he was "showered" in accordance with the suggestopedic method of teaching a foreign language.

As you know, vocabulary is a set of elements that are in regular relationships and together form a certain integrity. In the process of functioning, words are organized into a system and make it possible to discover such interrelationships that make the lexical-semantic system self-organizing. Only well-ordered, systematized and organized

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information is easier to remember and recall from memory. When it is necessary to use this or that word a person does not look over the entire dictionary, but somehow limits his search fulminantly.

Indeed, one of the main basic tasks in learning a foreign language is to increase the number of actively used words, which improves the literacy level of a person and introduces a significant variety in his speech. To memorize new words well, one needs to spend a considerable amount of time and make maximum efforts. Types of memory can be classified into three types: short-term (deals with the processing of information immediately at the moment of its receipt), medium-term (reproduces information received recently) and long-term (capable of storing part of the information throughout the life). In addition, memory can be passive or active. Thus, in order to replenish the vocabulary of the English language, you need to organize the memorization of new words so that the information is deposited in long-term memory and reproduced by its active department. This can be done quite simply if you use modern techniques for memorizing new information. As it's known, for the best development of communication skills, it is necessary to master new teaching methods and strategies aimed at developing activities such as speaking, reading, writing and listening.

Some of the tasks that foreign language teaching specialists suggest to expand vocabulary are as follows:

- working with texts: understanding the text based on certain keywords allows you to interpret and take the meaning of words out of the context that accompanies them, without the need to use the dictionary at any time;

- search for associations: the exercise is recommended for updating new terms that connect with certain images, definitions or other lexical units associated with them (synonyms, antonyms or words that are often used with them);

- classification: creating a family of words on a specific topic or one semantic or grammatical category, which allows you to organize the studied vocabulary for further use in appropriate contexts;

- exercises with phrases: the main condition for learning vocabulary words is practice, either in the form of creating written sentences that include new vocabulary, or its application in oral speech;

- games: the use of crosswords has a didactic and motivational power when learning new words in other languages.

Unfortunately, for a long time, the main principle of the format for constructing the old authoritarian system of language education was the relationship at the level of "instruction-fulfillment". Innovative and creative ideas, which make it possible to use these principles in a new format of language education, cause students to fear and unwillingness to revise their usual methods of work and use more effective innovative technologies. It is generally accepted that the development of communication skills occurs only with the presence of motivation and expression of their individuality.

For the successful introduction, consolidation and activation of vocabulary, we highlight the psychological and methodological aspects, as well as thematic and situational introduction of vocabulary. In the first approach, we select lexical units, the most common phrasal verbs, idioms, using visual materials, definitions, translation and method of linguistic guessing. Students make up dialogues, sentences, monologues, various situations. This stage, in my opinion, contributes to the consolidation of new vocabulary, speeds up the process of memorization. The studied lexical units are used in speech exercises and grammatical tasks, logical and associative connections are established. All these make it easier to memorize lexical units. All linguistic materials are systematized into thematic

groups of varying complexity. These thematic selections help us in developing lessons on a specific topic, taking into account individual peculiarities of students. Note that the center of communication is no longer in the linguistic plane, but in the plane of communication, and this, in our opinion, helps students to participate in maintaining conversation and in improving the quality of communication. This, in turn, allows students to get in touch with, listen to one another and receive feedback, express themselves as an individual, assert their point of view.

Thus, the conceptual basis for determining the target purpose of expanding vocabulary, content and learning strategies is precisely the sociocultural approach to language education, on the basis of which students would form knowledge about the realities and traditions of the country and would be included in the dialogue of cultures. Additional reading, watching video films, extracurricular activities and meetings with native speakers, participation in research work, in Internet projects, various vocabulary exercises of a training nature, clarity when introduced foreign language material play a crucial role in teaching ESL vocabulary.

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